

Complexes of Benzothiazole and 2-Substituted Benzothiazoles with Silver (I) -Co-ordination Number 2 and 3

R. N. DASH and D. V. RAMANA RAO

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-8.

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Twelve silver (I) complexes having the general formula $[AgL_2]X$ and $[AgL_3]X$ where L is benzothiazole (bt), 2-methyl benzothiazole (mbt) and 2-amino benzothiazole (ambt) have been prepared and characterised. Molar conductance and infra-red spectra ($5000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) show that nitrate and perchlorate groups are ionic giving rise to more usual two-coordinated compounds. The thiocyanate and cyanate groups, however, are coordinated to the metal forming three-coordinated complexes. Infra-red spectra in the range $700-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ reveal metal-sulphur bonding for all the complexes.

IN view of the biological importance of thiazole group, several workers have reported the study of co-ordination behaviour of simple and substituted thiazoles with bivalent transition metal ions¹⁻³. Thiazole group has both nitrogen and sulphur as possible donor sites and it has been found that majority of the complexes are nitrogen bonded. A case of sulphur co-ordination has been suggested by Duff et. al³. in the compound $[Cu_2(bt)_6]ClO_4$, where the ligand is probably acting as bridging ligand with co-ordination through sulphur and nitrogen. However, aminogroup in 2-position also provides an alternate donor site due to similar basicity of two nitrogen atoms in 2-amino benzothiazole. Silver (I), a strong class 'b' acceptor, has more affinity for sulphur than nitrogen and in fact, Gonick, Fernelius and Douglas⁴ have determined the formation constants of a series of sulphur and nitrogen containing chelates with ions of various transition metals and indicated that sulphur is a stronger donor than nitrogen for the silver ion. Therefore attempts have been made in this investigation to prepare complexes of benzothiazole, 2 methyl-and 2-amino benzothiazole with silver (I) salts with a view to see whether the bonding takes place through sulphur or nitrogen.

Experimental :

All the chemicals used for the reactions were of pure quality. Preparation of the complexes of the type, $[AgL_2]X$: The complexes were prepared by reacting an aqueous solution of silver (I) nitrate or perchlorate with benzothiazole, 2-methyl benzothiazole and hot aqueous solution of 2-amino benzothiazole in the stoich ometric ratio 1:2. The resulting mixtures were

shaken for fifteen minutes when white crystalline compounds (faint yellow in case of 2-amino benzothiazole) separated, which were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol, ether and then dried *in vacuo*. The complexes were insoluble in acetone, benzene and dimethyl formamide but fairly soluble in acetonitrile.

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[AgL_2]X$: Silver (I) thiocyanate or cyanate was dissolved in minimum quantity of liquor ammonia and was reacted with benzothiazole, 2-methyl benzothiazole and hot aqueous solution of 2-amino benzothiazole in the ratio 1:2. The resulting solutions were shaken for half an hour and kept over night. White needle shaped crystals with benzothiazole and 2-methyl benzothiazole and faint yellow amorphous solid with 2-amino benzothiazole were filtered off, washed with ether and then dried *in vacuo*. These complexes were insoluble in all common organic solvents excepting pyridine.

Physical measurement; Infra-red spectra were recorded in the range ($5000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to observe the shifts in frequencies of ligand absorption bands. The spectra were also recorded in some cases (Table 2) in the range $700-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to ascertain whether the ligands are bonded to the metal either through sulphur or nitrogen. Molar conductance was measured for $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solutions in acetonitrile or pyridine using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CLO102 and a dip type cell.

The relevant analytical and conductance data are given in Table 1 and the infra-red spectral data are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MELTING POINTS AND INFRA-RED SPECTRAL DATA (CM^{-1}) FOR ANIONS OF SILVER (I) COMPLEXES.

Compound	M.P. (°C)	%Silver		ΛM (mhos) Acetonitrile Pyridine	Anion band (CM^{-1})	
		Found	Calcd.			
1. $[Ag(bt)_2]NO_3$	132	24.2	24.5	130.1	1345s,	805s
2. $[Ag(bt)_2]ClO_4$	145	22.3	22.5	100.2	1090br.	
3. $[Ag(bt)_2]SCN$	273*	24.3	24.7	9.9	2080s,	740sh
4. $[Ag(bt)_2]NCO$	154	25.1	25.6	1.2	2130s,	1318s
5. $[Ag(mbt)_2]NO_3$	184	22.9	23.1	84.1	1323s,	820s
6. $[Ag(mbt)_2]ClO_4$	211	21.0	21.3	122.6	1090br.	
7. $[Ag(mbt)_2]SCN$	155	22.8	23.2	7.1	2060s,	737sh
8. $[Ag(mbt)_2]NCO$	163	23.8	24.0	7.9	2130s,	1320s
9. $[Ag(ambt)_2]NO_3$	221	22.5	22.9	128.5	1350m,	830m
10. $[Ag(ambt)_2]ClO_4$	260	20.7	21.2	94.5	1100br.	
11. $[Ag(ambt)_2]SCN$	211	22.9	23.2	4.5	2080s,	740m
12. $[Ag(ambt)_2]NCO$	208	23.5	23.9	7.3	2080s.	1318m.

* decompose, s-sharp, br-broad, m-medium.

TABLE 2—INFRA-RED ABSORPTION SPECTRA (700-400 CM⁻¹) OF THE LIGANDS AND SOME OF THE SILVER(I) COMPLEXES

bt.	Ag(bt) ₂ NO ₃	Ag(bt) ₂ CNO	mbt.	Ag(mbt) ₂ ClO ₄	Ag(mbt) ₂ SCN	ambt.	Ag(ambt) ₂ ^a NO ₃	Assignment
576w	565w	565w	668s	672w	672ms	625m	630w	Ligand vibration
500w	535w	535w	513w	563br.	565br	606w	—	
	505m	470w	476m	465s	465w	565m	525m	
420s	425s	420s	429s	430br	420m	526m	505m	
						500m	487s	ν(Ag-S) ν ₄ (ClO ₄) δ(NCO bending) δ(NCS bending)
						483s	423s	
—	670s	668w	—	672w	672w	428s	—	
		625vs		627s				
					465s			

Results and Discussion

Thiazole is formally derived from imidazole by replacement of NH by S in 1-position which makes thiazole a better π-acceptor due to availability of empty d-orbitals on sulphur atom. From the structures outlined below for thiazole it is expected that on co-ordination through either sulphur or nitrogen, C-S stretching vibration will increase in both the cases, while C=N stretching frequency will remain almost unaltered or may increase slightly for metal-sulphur bonding and will decrease for metal-nitrogen bonding. However, substituent in 2-position may effect the resulting system.

The I.R. spectra of benzothiazole and 2-substituted benzothiazoles show a strong band at ~1500 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to C=N stretching vibration in analogy to thiourea and other ligands containing similar group vibration. While this band remains almost unaltered in benzothiazole complexes, the 2-methyl and 2-amino benzothiazole complexes show rather a peculiar behaviour. The original single sharp band at 1541 cm⁻¹ in 2-methyl benzothiazole is split up into three components and while two are shifted to higher frequencies the third one is lowered by 20-30 cm⁻¹. In case of 2-amino benzothiazole complexes, however the split up bands are shifted to higher frequency regions. It is thus not very clear to draw any general conclusion from the shifts in ν(C-N). Similarly the C-S stretching frequency also does not offer any definite conclusion. Hence it was thought worthwhile to record the I. R. spectra in 700-400 cm⁻¹ region to see whether any direct evidence can be obtained for either Ag-N or Ag-S bonding in the complexes.

In the table-2 are recorded the infra-red absorption frequencies of the ligands and complexes in the range 700-400 cm⁻¹. All the complexes show a sharp band at ~670 cm⁻¹ in addition to the ligand vibrations, which in all probability can be assigned to silver-sulphur stretching frequency as shown later. In 2-methyl-benzothiazole complexes, however, this ν(Ag-S) band is not independently distinguishable since it is overlapped in that

region by a ligand vibration. Although normal co-ordinate analysis would provide the M-S stretching force constant, we have calculated approximate value for Ag-S stretching frequency by using the formula⁵

$$\nu(\text{Cm}^{-1}) = \frac{1}{2\pi C} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where C=velocity of light, μ=reduced mass, k=force constant.

which finally becomes

$$\nu(\text{Cm}^{-1}) = 1307 \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Taking a value of 5 × 10⁵ dynes/cm for k and substituting the values of k and μ in the above equation it is found that ν(Ag-S) and ν(Ag-N) occur round about 650 and 850 cm⁻¹ respectively. The complexes under study do not show any additional new band at ~850 cm⁻¹ but a prominent band is observed at ~670 cm⁻¹ in each of the complexes which can only be assigned to Ag-S stretching frequency.

In case of 2-amino benzothiazole complexes it is observed that the ν(N-H) bands remain unaltered at ~3350 cm⁻¹, which shows the non-involvement of amino group in the complex formation.

Three I.R. active vibrations-ν₄, a doubly degenerate inplane bending, ν₃, a doubly degenerate stretch and ν₂, an out of plane deformation are expected for the nitrate ion⁶ (D_{3h} symmetry). The ν₄ region is covered by a strong vibration due to aromatic rings. The ν₂ and ν₃ vibrations are observed for all the nitrate complexes at ~1320 and 820 cm⁻¹ respectively (table 1). For the perchlorate, the asymmetric stretching band of the anion (ν₃) is observed⁷ as a broad band in the region 1050-1170 cm⁻¹ and the bands observed for the perchlorate compounds lie well in this range (Table 1) indicating the presence of an ionic perchlorate group. The ionic nature of the nitrate and perchlorate group is also in conformity with conductance measurements (Table 1), which show them to be 1:1 electrolytes.

The thiocyanato complexes exhibit⁸-three vibrations, namely νC-N, νC-S and δ(NCS bending) in the regions 2150-2080, 810-690 and 500-400 cm⁻¹ respectively. The complexes reported now show a sharp band at ~20.0 cm⁻¹, which in comparison⁹ with the other S-bonded thiocyanate co-ordination, can be assigned to C≡N stretching frequency. Frago and James¹⁰ suggested that the ν(C-S) frequency drops in S-bonded thiocyanate complexes relative to that in KSCN, which can be a useful guide to the mode of thiocyanate bonding.

Accordingly, the bands at $\sim 740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 1) are assigned to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ vibration of S-bonded thiocyanate group. The δNCS bending vibration was however recorded only in one compound at 465 cm^{-1} (Table 2).

For the cyanato complexes, the location of ν_{asy} , ν_{sy} and $\delta(\text{NCO bending})$ are indicative¹¹ of the mode of bonding in the complexes. The ν_{asy} , which appears as a strong band at 2200 cm^{-1} undergoes a small shift to lower frequencies on passing from terminal to bridging condition. However, the position of ν_{sy} or $\nu(\text{C-O})$ is diagnostic to distinguish between N-bonded and O-bonded complexes on account of their wide difference in band positions. In the present investigation, the $\nu(\text{C-O})$ bands are observed at $\sim 1305 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that cyanate group is bonded to the metal through nitrogen and this is well supported by earlier work^{1,2}. The low values for Λ_{M} (Table 1) indicating a non-electrolytic nature of thiocyanato and cyanato complexes are in conformity with the anionic co-ordination indicated by I.R. spectra.

Thus co ordination number 3 for the metal ion is established in case of thiocyanato and cyanato complexes and the more usual co-ordination number 2 is indicated for nitrate and perchlorate compounds.

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